

THE USE OF FOOD DYES (E-171, E-173) AND THE CHANGES CAUSED BY THEM

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Annotation

Food additives or food dyes (E-171, E-173) are substances added for technological purposes to give the necessary properties and qualities to products during production, packaging, transportation or storage. They are used as certain dyes, flavors, and preservatives (Alyakhnovich, N.S., 2015; Alyakhnovich N.S., Novikov D.K., 2016). These dyes are used in the cosmetics industry, in the production of cigarettes, oil, flour, toothpaste, confectionery, chewing gum, candy, fast food, beverages, cheese and many other products, as well as in the pharmaceutical industry. According to the chemical composition, these food additives are E-171 titanium dioxide, E-173 aluminum. E-171 titanium dioxide - formula TiO_2 .

Key words: E-171, E-173, preservative, xenobiotic, cytotoxic.

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изменения.**Аннотация**

Пищевые добавки или пищевые красители (Е-171, Е-173) – это вещества, добавляемые в технологических целях для придания продукции необходимых свойств и качеств в процессе производства, упаковки, транспортировки или хранения. Их используют в качестве определенных красителей, ароматизаторов, консервантов, продуктов консервации (Аляхнович, Н.С., 2015; Аляхнович Н.С., Новиков Д.К., 2016). Эти красители используются в косметической промышленности, производства сигарет, масла, муки, зубной пасты, кондитерских изделий, добавляют в состав жевательных резинок, конфет, фаст-фуда, напитков, сыра и многих других продуктов, а также в фармацевтической промышленности. По химическому составу эти пищевые добавки Е-171 - диоксид титана, Е-173 - алюминий. Е-171-диоксид титана - формула TiO_2 .

Relevance of the problem. Currently, some components of food products and most of the medicines can become xenobiotics and produce harmful substances in the body. They can have allergenic, mutagenic, carcinogenic or cytotoxic effects. Pollution of water and air on Earth, depletion of natural resources, disruption of natural processes directly or indirectly affects the human body. Therefore, it is important to analyze the components of food, medicine, and the tools we use for our needs, to study their effects on the body.

Е-171 is titanium dioxide and is a food additive. Its formula is TiO_2 . This substance is used as a food coloring, moisturizing and long-term preservation agent. Titanium dioxide is used in products such as white flour, table salt, sugar, chewing gum, toothpaste, soap, detergents, chemicals, vitamin pills, confectionery, soda and baking powder. Due to their light reflecting, whiteness and concealing properties, they are used in the paint industry and in cosmetics with whitening, thickening and sun blocking properties. Titanium dioxide is one

of the three main materials used in nanotechnology. Titanium dioxide is used as a colorant and preservative in nanotechnological paints and in all medical preparations. Titanium dioxide is a chemically stable substance that does not break down in the body. Titanium dioxide nanocrystals also have the property of photocatalysis. Photocatalysis is a substance that helps to carry out certain reactions with light, and it works by destroying organic particles that come into contact with the body. Titanium dioxide decomposes organic matter in air, water and various surfaces to form water and carbon dioxide. Self-cleaning paints and fabrics are also made from this substance. When the fabric or paint surface is coated with titanium dioxide crystals, the organic matter in contact with these coated parts is broken down and various organic stains are removed. Some studies have shown that titanium dioxide can cause inflammation in the gut and an increase in free radicals in the tissues, so this substance is stored in the body. This stored substance has the ability to destroy organic particles. Since they are strong moisture retainers, they disrupt the body's water balance. This substance damages both single and double strands of DNA. Thus, it damages chromosomes and disrupts gene structure. Free radicals can damage cells and tissues, increase the risk of developing various diseases such as cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and also accelerate the aging process. Other studies have shown that inhaling titanium dioxide powder can cause lung and body damage. In addition, it was found that this dye makes it difficult to absorb some vitamins and minerals. European food safety regulators have declared titanium dioxide unsafe for human consumption due to its potential toxicity. Titanium is not considered a toxic metal, but it is a heavy metal and it has serious negative health effects. Titanium has the ability to affect lung function causing lung diseases such as pleurisy, which can cause chest pain with congestion, difficulty breathing, coughing, skin or eye irritation possible. Currently, the neurotoxic effects of TiO₂ NPs have only been evaluated through animal models, including rats, mice, and zebrafish, and cell

studies, including primary neurons, PC12, and SH-SY5Y cell lines. TiO₂ NPs can induce oxidative stress, increase neuroinflammation, alter brain biochemistry, or damage neurons.

Aluminum is a chemical element with the formula Al, atomic number 13, and it is a silver-white, soft, non-magnetic and malleable metal belonging to the boron group in Mendeleev's periodic table. By mass, aluminum makes up about 8% of the Earth's crust; It is one of the most abundant elements in the earth's crust, after oxygen and silicon. The main ore of aluminum is bauxite. Aluminum metal is very chemically active and is found in more than 70 different mineral compounds. Aluminum is distinguished by its low density and difficulty in corrosion. Oxides and sulfates are the most useful and common compounds of aluminum. Despite the widespread distribution of aluminum on the earth's surface, aluminum salts are not used in the metabolic process in living organisms. E173 paints, i.e. give aluminum products a bright silver color. It is used in the production of foil for food. It is used in confectionery, flour products, pharmaceuticals. A particularly high concentration of aluminum is observed in canned drinks, which are used in the inner packaging of aluminum containers and drinks. There are assumptions that the constant consumption of aluminum in food may be associated with the development of certain diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease, various neurological diseases and allergic reactions. In Russia and Ukraine, the use of the E173 additive in the food industry is prohibited. In addition, E173 dye is banned in Australia and a number of other countries. While most studies suggest that normal amounts of aluminum in food are not harmful to human health, most of these studies have been conducted in animals or in vitro, and more research is needed to evaluate the effects in humans.

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